
The Model of Green Product Diversity and Price on Interest in Buying Batik Dahon Pangandaran

Feby Febrian¹, Adriza², Granit Agustina³, Rudi Suprianto Ahmadi⁴

^{1,4} Universitas Winaya Mukti & Jl. Turangga No. 25 Bandung, Indonesia

² Akademi Sekretari Manajemen Kencana & Jl Wastu Kencana No 5c Bandung, Indonesia

³ Universitas Kebangsaan Republik Indonesia & Jl Pelajar Pejuang 45 no 8 Bandung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study has three variables, namely green product (x1), price (x2) and buying interest (y) which aims by explore product quality, price and buying interest in Pangandaran Dahon batik. By this way the research is quantitative by descriptive and verification approach. Primary data collection techniques obtained through questionnaires, observations and interviews. Secondary data obtained through the library and documents that were reviewed. The population is 100 consumers of Batik Dahon Pangandaran. The effect of green product and price on buying interest is used multiple linear regression analysis or path analysis and determinant coefficients with the help of SPSS for window 24. Green products and prices with buying interest in Batik Dahon Pangandaran and respondents' results from the questionnaire answers turned out to be green products and The price on buying interest in Batik Dahon Pangandaran as a whole shows a positive and good response. Obtained on batik Dahon Pangandaran and others influenced by other factors.

KEYWORDS: Green Product, Price, Buying Interest

1. INTRODUCTION

Green product or green product is something that does not pollute the air and the environment, preserves resources or can be reprocessed. By using green products, everything related to pollution, toxic substances, and waste can be eliminated or reduced by our way of saving, maintaining and increasing energy or energy from natural environmental resources, Shabani et al (2013). It is explained that a green product is a product that has long durability, is good for health and is not dangerous and can be reprocessed in materials and packaging forms, Ottman (2010). Through the above understanding, it can be understood that a green product is a product that is safe to use and is able to maintain the cleanliness of the surrounding environment.

An organization that does not know how to respond to a customer's wants, needs, needs, tastes and interest in buying processes will fail both in terms of sales and marketing, Therefore the company or organization must have creativity that is able to innovate and be environmentally friendly so that it can compete.

Fierce competition in the world of trade occurs in various things in the form of clothing trade, the need in the form of cloth is a person's basic basic obligation that must be available so that the clothing business, especially batik, becomes popular in the Pangandaran Indonesian community. The growth of high rivalry compared to clothing must implement the right marketing method so that customers get something needed by customers causing satisfaction for users of these products. Companies are asked to thoroughly understand the overall needs and expectations of customers or companies must be able to produce similar products for the needs of environmentally friendly customers. Not only that, it is treated well by marketing. customers start to feel happy if they get the results of their supervision showing that the products that have been used are popular as well as environmentally friendly or superior green products, not only famous from the attention of the local population but also from the views of the surrounding community. Therefore, many customers will buy it, the quality of a product, namely a product that has a healthy value for environmental insight and good quality will be the target of customers to fulfill their needs. In the international multilateral market that creates green products and prices as the central foundation to foster buying interest as something special for customers to ensure alternative products in increasing their needs. Research conducted by Nur Haqiqi and Widwi Handari Adji (2021) said that product quality has led to the stage of customer buying interest in a process that focuses only on quality and interest, excluding products that are environmentally sound. Tamara Izzani (2021) conducted a study that revealed when the green market had a significant impact to a purchase regulation that is not a green product and consumer buying interest, then the life attitude model has a good and significant impact on consumer choice in buying products and research conducted by Rissa Mustika Sari and Prihartono (2021) namely that purchasing decisions on RISE bed linen are influenced by price and quality of bed linen, do not focus on green products

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and consumer buying interest. This research seeks to understand the impact of green products and prices on consumer buying interest in Pangandaran Koja batik Good environmental insight.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Green product

Anggraeni, R. and Susilowati, C. (2022) say that many companies produce environmentally friendly goods and offer their products with varied and attractive marketing mix strategies. One of the company's potential target markets is millennials because the growth in the number of this community has become very large. In terms of behavior, the millennial generation has a high level of consumption compared to other generations. However, there are big questions about millennials' willingness to consume eco-friendly products. This study intends to understand the act of purchasing environmentally friendly products among millennials, especially green products. The importance of preserving the environment and having a group that cares about the environment will have a pro-environmental attitude and are willing to buy environmentally friendly products, even though they have a higher price and still have high buying interest. Green products can use the results to formulate effective green marketing strategies to attract consumer buying interest. Kim et al (2022), said that the green product strategy as a source of competitive advantage and in turn improve the company's performance. green product strategy may face managerial difficulties because it is considered too expensive in terms of price resulting in a reduced number of enthusiasts. Kautish, Pradeep; Sharma, Rajesh (2018) said that the essential goal of green consumption such as buying environmentally friendly products even though they are expensive compared to other options causes differences in utility-oriented consumption such as product reuse or recycling. Limiting that environmental values are determined by one's locus on two orthogonal dimensions: first, a biocentric dimension that leads to environmental conservation and protection and, second, an anthropocentric dimension that echoes the use of natural resources. Johannes et al (2015) said that in growing Green Product, it is known that the Green Product performance dimensions include product energy based, product driven, product pollution and product packing.

Price

Armstrong, Kotler (2015) said that price is a simple and dynamic marketing element so that it can move based on company direction. The price also has a quality that is in accordance with the value of the product and others. The indicators applied include prices based on product quality, easily accessible prices, competitive prices and prices that have the benefits of Kotler (2015). Guzman, Francisco; Linde, Frank (2009) said that the price in principle is to sell the same product to each customer at a different price. Prices should not be cost oriented but should be market oriented. For this reason, a good customer is certain to have to pay through the market (online) or the customer must at least partly on a purchase given the opportunity to reveal how the asking price is. Yiu Wah Ho, R., Strange, R., & Piesse, J. (2013) said that conditional prices are knowledge about the behavior of market capital that has broad implications for financial decisions. Adel et al (2022) say that there are five dimensions of price perception, namely price awareness, price mavenism, sales, price quality schemes, and prestige sensitivity on the value perceived by consumers such as acquisition value and transaction value and how perceived value affects consumer behavior in the form of intention. or interests such as purchase intentions and intentions to recommend. Consumer behavior intentions towards good or suboptimal products are positively influenced by both dimensions of perceived value. In addition, perceived value is influenced by different price perception dimensions that moderate the relationship between perceived value and behavioral intentions.

Buying Interest

Febrian, Feby (2019) argues that buying interest is consumer interest in transacting a product that has a certain value by considering certain feelings or decisions about a product. Feng, N., Zhang, A., van Klinken, R.D. and Cui, L. (2021) said that buying interest in the image of clean green products is the strongest form of desire to buy through increasing trust in the quality of a product. Guo, Gongxing; Tu, Hongwei; Cheng, Bao (2018) argue that product trust mediates a positive relationship between consumer affinity and willingness to buy, that product trust is positively related to willingness to buy, can also moderate the intensity of the mediating effect for product trust in the relationship between consumers and desire to buy. Isaac Cheah Ian Phau Calvin Chong Anwar Sadat Shimul, (2015) revealed that the notion of visibility as well as cognitive and affective bonds that connect brands with consumers have been defined as brand advantages by considering the importance of social visibility and emotional connection for luxury brands, it is very important to include excellence brands in buying interest in luxury brands. According to Fredinand (2002:129) buying interest can be identified through the dimensions of transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest and exploratory interest. According to Faradiba (2013: 2), buying interest occurs when customers feel they have to fulfill their various needs by actualizing what they need and want accompanied by encouragement that comes from their views.

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Fig1. State of the art

3. RESEARCH METHODS

By using purposive sampling, which is a way of taking samples of quality values (Sugiyono, 2017:25). Dahon batik has a population of up to 100 people so that in this study 58 samples were obtained which were obtained through the use of the slovin formula. By using various research instruments such as facts, symbols, codes, numbers that can be understood become things that must be known. Using primary sources in the form of distributing questionnaires, interviews and observations as well as several sources from the library, agency documents and learning notes on campus which are secondary sources at the research site.

The research materials obtained are in the form of discussions and development of field practices in compiling the concept of green products, prices and buying interest in the research structure which are then collected and developed as a forum for knowledge to be studied at the level of basic problems, brief material explanations and implementation. Carry out a business plan in accordance with the green product concept, price and buying interest in the research structure that has been poured.

Furthermore, this information is assessed, analyzed by narrative or statistical descriptions that are processed through path analysis and determinant coefficients to see their size based on the level of validity in a questionnaire. When it is that this questionnaire is valid or valid, it is able to assess and measure these variables correctly. And used product moment correlation. In the level of confidence how much the results can be measured, the reliability of the instrument is used repeatedly. Alpha cronbac is used as a method in data collection both independent and dependent to be able to test hypotheses through the obtained samples. various impacts of a number of research variables on green products, prices and consumer buying interest as a research, as well as information that is implemented by means of path analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Obtained the results of testing the instrument validity of green product (x1)

Table 1. green produk validity (x1)

No	Statement	r-count
1	X-1	,879
2	X-2	,706
3	X-3	,673
4	X-4	,772
5	X-5	,669
6	X-6	,769
7	X-7	,615
8	X-8	,667

Source: 2022 data processing

It was obtained that the green product instrument testing was declared valid.

Obtained the results of testing the validity of the price instrument (x2)

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Table 2. Price Validity (x2)

No	statement	r-count
1	X ₋₁	,379
2	X ₋₋₂	,481
3	X ₋₃	,620
4	X ₋₄	,573
5	X ₋₅	,477
6	X ₋₆	,820
7	X ₋₇	,491
8	X ₋₈	,439
9	X ₋₉	.487
10	X ₋₁₀	.565

Source: 2022 data processing

It was obtained that the price instrument test was declared valid

Obtained the results of testing the validity of the purchase interest instrument (y)

Table 3. Buying interest validity (y)

No	statement	R-count
1	y-1	,669
2	y-2	,687
3	y-3	,715
4	y-4	,610
5	y-5	,459
6	y-6	,379
7	y-7	,757
8	y-8	,453

Source: 2022 data processing

It was obtained that the purchase interest instrument test was declared valid.

Reliability Results

Table 4. Instrumental Reliability Testing

variabel	Statement	Standar
Green Product	0.744	0.6
Price	0.752	0.6
Buying Interest	0.698	0.6

Source: 2022 data processing

The results of the instrument test are declared as reliability with a coefficient above 0.6

Recapitulation of green product variable was obtained

Table 5. Recapitulation of green product variables

No	Statement	score	Description
1	Dahon batik uses natural ingredients	245	Strongly agree
2	Dahon batik uses renewable ones	247	agree
3	Dahon batik raw materials are in the surrounding natural environment	244	agree
4	Dahon batik raw materials are easy to obtain	251	Strongly agree
5	Dahon batik material is good safe for our bodies	244	agree
6	Dahon batik material does not use harmful chemicals	239	enough
7	Dahon batik packaging can be recycled	240	enough
8	Environmentally healthy Dahon batik packaging	243	enough

Source: 2022 data processing

The results obtained from the recapitulation of green product 251, the raw material for batik dahon Pangandaran is easy to obtain. This shows that the green product of Dahon Pangandaran batik is good.

Obtained Recapitulation of price variables

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Table 6. Recapitulation of price variables

No	Statement	Score	Description
1	The price is according to the quality of the product	252	Strongly agree
2	Price according to taste	244	enough
3	The price is affordable	250	Strongly agree
4	Prices offered are flexible	246	agree
5	The price is competitive	245	agree
6	The price is average	238	enough
7	The price is cheap	239	enough
8	The price is not expensive	243	enough

Source: 2022 data processing

The results obtained from the price recapitulation are 252, batik dahon Pangandaran is priced according to product quality. This shows that the price of Batik Dahon Pangandaran is good.

Obtained a recapitulation of buying interest variables

Table 7. Recapitulation of buying interest variables

No	Statement	Score	Description
1	I will buy Dahon batik	253	Strongly agree
2	I will buy a promo package for Dahon batik	255	Strongly agree
3	I will buy Dahon batik because of reference	247	agree
4	I will buy Dahon batik because of a friend's suggestion	245	agree
5	I bought Dahon batik according to the motif I like	248	agree
6	I bought Dahon batik according to my taste	249	agree
7	Getting information about Dahon batik is very important	242	enough
8	The offer of new Dahon batik products is very important	241	enough

Source: 2022 data processing

The results obtained from the recapitulation of buying interest are 255, interested in buying a promo package for batik dahon Pangandaran. This shows that the interest in buying Batik Dahon Pangandaran is good.

Obtained SPSS research results

Table 8 SPSS Result

Model		Coefficients ^a				Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	9.807	4.266		2.299	.029
	Green Product	.817	.186	.682	4.333	.667
	Price	.611	.140	.721	4.372	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

The path coefficient value is obtained

Table 9. path coefficient values

Path Coefficient	Value	description
P_{Y, X_1}	.682	There is an effect of green product on buying interest
P_{Y, X_2}	.721	There is an effect of price on buying interest

Source: 2022 data processing

The calculation is obtained above the green product (X1) and with a buying interest of 0.682 and a price (X2) with a buying intention of 0.721.

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Obtained partial test

Table 10. Partial test

No	Hipotesis	t-count	t-Tabel	Path coefficient	decesion	description
1.	P_Y, X_1	4.333	1.6972	0.682	rejected	Signifikan
2.	P_Y, X_2	4.372	1.6972	0.721	rejected	Signifikan

Source: 2022 data processing

The effect of green product on buying interest

The impact of green product on buying interest is 0.682, meaning that the better the green product, the better the interest in buying the dahon batik. Hadika Sofwan and Candra Wijayaangka (2021) that Green Product and Green Price have a positive and significant impact simultaneously and partially on Purchasing Decisions. Kim, J et al (2022), stated that green product strategy is a source of competitive advantage and in turn improves company performance. Green product strategies may face managerial difficulties because they are considered too expensive in terms of price which results in a decrease in the number of applicants. Kautish, Pradeep; Sharma, Rajesh (2018) said that the essential goals of green consumption such as buying environmentally friendly products even though they are expensive compared to other options lead to differences in utility-oriented consumption such as product reuse or recycling. And it can be concluded that according to Kotler and Keller (2016: 12) producers are able to provide healthy products that do not adversely affect the environment and conversely provide benefits in protecting their green products.

The effect of price on buying interest is 0.721, meaning that the price will get better when the buying interest of the Dahon batik product gets better. According to Arrahma Elian Tania, Haris Hemawan and Ahmad Izzuddin. (2022) that place (X1) and price (X2) simultaneously have a significant impact on buying interest in Bumdes Ajong Rejo. This means that location and price have an influence on buying interest. Armstrong, Kotler (2015) said that price is a very dynamic marketing element because it can adjust based on company direction. The price seems to indicate the quality of the accompanying product. Guzman, Francisco; Linde, Frank (2009) said that the price in principle is to sell the same product to each customer at a different price.

5. CONCLUSION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATION

Dahon batik as a whole has a very good green product and is much desired by consumers, especially the models, motifs, materials, combinations and images. It is just In developing and improving products there is something that is of major concern, including brand, design and durability of these products which are considered to be lacking for consumer tastes. The price of Koja batik is in accordance with consumer expectations, especially in terms of affordability and is quite cheap and not too expensive. However, there are still a number of things that must be improved immediately, including the price is still not flexible, there are still prices that are not in accordance with quality, are not in accordance with taste and competition and can still be considered mediocre. Buying interest in Dahon batik is good, among others, that consumers are very interested in using the brand, therefore a number of things must be improved, including that the brand is still not trusted, not convincing, there are still those who don't like it, still don't want to use it again, not interested in buying it again and don't want to buy the brand again. In the study it was found that simultaneously green product and price had an impact on buying interest in Dahon Pangandaran batik and partially green product was not more dominant than price on buying interest in Dahon Pangandaran batik. In the future, further research will be conducted on issues of brand image, consumer satisfaction and consumer experience.

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